

Statistical review of
*Comparative Effectiveness and Safety of Ribavirin Plus Interferon-Alpha,
Lopinavir/Ritonavir Plus Interferon-Alpha and Ribavirin Plus
Lopinavir/Ritonavir Plus Interferon-Alpha in Patients with Mild to Moderate
Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia: Results of a Randomized, Open-Labeled
Prospective Study*

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The following review has been prepared in collaboration with members of the MRC-NIHR Trials Methodology Research Partnership¹. The reviewers named above, and other, unnamed discussants of the paper, are all qualified statisticians with experience in clinical trials. Our objective is to provide a rapid review of publications, preprints and protocols from clinical trials of COVID-19 treatments, independent of journal specific review processes. We aim to provide timely, constructive, focused, clear advice aimed at improving both the research outputs under review, as well as future studies. Given our collective expertise (clinical trial statistics) our reviews focus on the designs of the trials and other statistical content (methods, presentation and accuracy of results, inferences). This review reflects the expert opinions of the named authors, and does not imply endorsement by the MRC-NIHR Trials Methodology Research Partnership, its wider membership, or any other organization.

Here we review *Comparative Effectiveness and Safety of Ribavirin Plus Interferon-Alpha, Lopinavir/Ritonavir Plus Interferon-Alpha and Ribavirin Plus Lopinavir/Ritonavir Plus Interferon-Alpha in Patients with Mild to Moderate Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia: Results of a Randomized, Open-Labeled Prospective Study* by Chen *et al*², published on the SSRN preprint server on the 5th May.

Overall, this was a well-conducted and reported randomised controlled trial, but it was likely too small to detect small but clinically meaningful effects. While the authors concluded that the results “clearly indicate” there were no differences between the study arms, in our opinion the trial would be more accurately interpreted as inconclusive. The comparison of three active treatment regimens with no standard-of-care arm further complicated the interpretation of the trial.

Study Summary

The paper reports a three-arm parallel randomised controlled trial in patients hospitalized with rt-PCR confirmed COVID-19 and mild to moderate illness. The study aimed to recruit 108 patients from the Chongqing Public Health Medical Centre (China) between January 29 and February 25, 2020. Patients were randomised using a 1:1:1 allocation ratio into one of three arms: ribavirin (intravenous loading dose of 2g, followed by oral doses between 600 and 800 mg every 8 hours for 14 days) plus interferon- α (inhalation of 50mg twice a day for 14 days); interferon- α plus lopinavir–ritonavir (400 mg / 100 mg twice a day for 14 days); or ribavirin, interferon- α , and lopinavir–ritonavir in a triple combination.

The primary outcome was time to a negative rt-PCR for SARS-CoV-2. Key secondary outcomes were the proportion of patients with a negative rt-PCR for SARS-CoV-2 at day 14; mortality at day 28; and the proportion of patients that progressed to severe illness by day 28.

A total of 101 patients were recruited and randomised, with 33 in the ribavirin plus interferon- α arm, 36 in the interferon- α plus lopinavir–ritonavir arm, and 32 in the triple combination arm. In the intention-to-treat analysis, the median times to a negative rt-PCR for SARS-CoV-2 for the three groups were, respectively, 13 days, 12 days, and 15 days (log-rank test $p = 0.23$), while the proportions of patients with a negative result at day 14 were 0.51, 0.61, and 0.47 ($p > 0.05$). Results were similarly inconclusive in the per-protocol sample ($n = 27, 28, 21$). There were no deaths in any arm. Finally, the authors reported that there was a significant increase in gastrointestinal adverse events in the ribavirin and lopinavir–ritonavir arm compared to the other two.

Based on these findings, the authors concluded that there were “no significant differences among the three regimens in terms of antiviral effectiveness in patients with mild to moderate COVID-19” and that the combination of ribavirin and lopinavir–ritonavir should not be co-administered to COVID-19 patients simultaneously.

We sincerely thank the authors for their contribution to our collective understanding of COVID-19, for their commitment to the timely dissemination of research results.

Major comments

Having three active treatment arms with no standard-of-care control complicates the interpretation of the trial results.

The authors did not include a standard-of-care control group in the study. Consequently, the study lacked *assay sensitivity*; while the design allows a comparison of the relative performance of the three treatment regimens, it would not allow us to conclude that any of them are superior to standard of care. Additionally, similar outcomes between groups would be compatible with all three lacking efficacy, but also with all three conferring the same level of benefit. The authors suggest that the failure to detect significant differences between the groups suggests that none of the regimens are efficacious, since it is unlikely that all three would have the same antiviral efficacy. However, this is based on the assumption that lack of statistical significance indicates an equivalence of effects, which is not warranted (see next point).

The authors might have also considered a factorial design³, whereby the study results could be used to directly estimate the effects of each individual treatment, and test for interactions among them, rather than trying to infer these from between-group comparisons.

The authors noted that a placebo or standard-of-care control group was not included due to ethical considerations, and due to restrictions imposed by national guidelines. However this seems at odds with other trials coming out of China which have used standard of care as a control, e.g. Cao *et al*⁴.

Recommendations:

For future studies

- Studies should include a suitable control arm to ensure that differences between groups, or lack thereof, can be unambiguously interpreted. Where researchers wish to evaluate combinations of therapies, a factorial design might offer a more efficient way to do this.

For this study

- It would be difficult to interpret differences between groups (or lack thereof) in this study, without recourse to external knowledge about the efficacy of one of the tested regimens.

The study was not well powered for moderate but clinically meaningful effects.

Though there was a lack of clarity in the description of the sample size calculation (in particular there was no target effect size noted in the paper or the protocol), clearly this study was not well powered to detect anything other than large effects, leaving it ill-equipped to detect smaller but still clinically relevant effects. Consequently, it isn't appropriate to interpret the statistically insignificant results as evidence of no effect⁵, as the authors do.

Recommendations:

For future studies

- Trials should be powered on the basis of relevant, realistic effect sizes. At the interpretation stage, it is crucial that imprecise, nonsignificant effects are not declared as

indicating a lack of difference between groups. It may be more accurate to describe a trial as being 'inconclusive' in this scenario.

For this study

- Rather than concluding there was no difference in outcomes between the treatment groups, it would be more appropriate to say that the trial was inconclusive, in that the relative performance of the studied regimens remains unclear.

Overall suboptimal presentation of results

The presentation of results restricts the ability to interpret the findings of the study. The paper reports the outcomes in each group, but these should be complemented by differences between arms with confidence intervals, in order to allow readers to gauge the information provided by the study. The authors have also described statistical inferences in a binary manner (as significant or not). Exact p-values would be more informative. No parameter estimates are shown for any of the outcomes apart from the primary, for which hazard ratios are reported.

Recommendations:

For future studies

- Differences between (or ratios of) group outcomes should be reported, together with a measure of uncertainty (such as confidence interval). Authors should report exact (appropriately rounded) p-values, instead of just reporting whether or not a statistical test yielded a significant result.

Minor points

- Patients and clinicians in the study were not blinded to treatment allocation, though other trial staff dealing with assessment/data collection (e.g. for adverse events) were. The authors note that there was centralized randomization and strict patient recruitment criteria, and while that might help to reassure that there was no selection bias in patients enrolling onto the study, it doesn't address the lack of blinding as the authors state. Thus performance and detection bias are still threats to the internal validity of the trial.

- The paper only reports unadjusted treatment effects, whereas adjustment for important prognostic factors measured at baseline (factors which should be pre-registered, prior to data collection) would have led to more precisely estimated treatment effects⁶. A multivariable Cox regression was prespecified in the published protocol, but apparently not reported. If the hazard ratios in the manuscript were in fact adjusted, it is unclear what was adjusted for.

- There was only a limited description of the process used to maintain allocation concealment. The registry entry states “Subjects included in the study after clinical diagnosis by the research leader, then use Excel to generate random schemes” while the paper refers to “centralization of randomisation”. Based on the limited description provided, we believe that allocation was concealed. If however allocation was not prospectively concealed, this would constitute a threat to study validity.

- Several outcomes, including the timings of assessment, are imprecisely defined, and there are possible inconsistencies in how they are reported. For example, 'mortality at 28 days' is reported as 'mortality during the study', and we must assume that these refer to the same period. Another example is length of hospital stay, which is reported in the outcomes but does not appear to have been prespecified.

Open Data

No.

Open Analysis Code

No.

Pre-registered study design

The trial was preregistered on 2020-01-29 (ChiCTR2000029387).

PubPeer

There may be comments on the PubPeer page for the published version of this paper.
<https://pubpeer.com/publications/2FFA2B5F4FFE470FF551E805AE198C>

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CONSORT CHECKLIST

To support the review, we completed the CONSORT checklist⁷ below. Material taken directly from the paper (or trial registry) is in *italics*. Our additional comments are in **bold**.

Title and abstract

1a Identification as a randomised trial in the title

Yes

1b Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions.

Title: Identification of the study as randomised	Yes
Authors: Contact details for the corresponding author	Yes
Trial design: Description of the trial design (eg, parallel, cluster, non-inferiority)	Yes
Methods	
Participants: Eligibility criteria for participants and the settings where the data were collected	No
Interventions: Interventions intended for each group	Yes
Objective: Specific objective or hypothesis	Yes
Outcome: Clearly defined primary outcome for this report	Yes
Randomisation: How participants were allocated to interventions	Yes
Blinding (masking): Whether or not participants, care givers, and those assessing the outcomes were blinded to group assignment	Yes
Results	
Numbers randomised: Number of participants randomised to each group	No
Recruitment: Trial status	No
Numbers analysed: Number of participants analysed in each group	No
Outcome: For the primary outcome, a result for each group and the estimated effect size and its precision	No
Harms: Important adverse events or side-effects	Yes
Conclusions: General interpretation of the results	Yes
Trial registration: Registration number and name of trial register	Yes
Funding: Source of funding	Yes

Introduction

Background and objectives

2a Scientific background and explanation of rationale

Yes.

2b Specific objectives or hypotheses

Based on studies of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS), and the Chinese guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of COVID-19, we conducted a clinical trial with the objective of comparing the effectiveness of three antiviral treatment regimens in patients with mild to moderate COVID-19.

Methods

Trial design

3a Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio

This present study was a single-center, open-labeled, randomized, prospective clinical trial, which included eligible patients diagnosed with mild to moderate COVID-19.

All eligible patients were block randomized individually by means of random computer-generated lists, to one of three treatment groups: RBV+IFN- α , LPV/r+IFN- α , and RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α , with an allocation ratio of 1:1:1...

3b Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons

None given.

Participants

4a Eligibility criteria for participants

Patients included in our study had to satisfy the following eligibility criteria: (1) 18-65 years of age; (2) diagnosed as mild to moderate COVID-19; (3) willing to sign informed consent. We excluded patients if they: (1) were pregnant or breastfeeding women; (2) had aspartate aminotransferase (AST) or alanine aminotransferase (ALT) >5×UNL, creatinine clearance <50 ml/min; (3) were allergic or intolerant to therapeutic drugs; (4)

were HIV-positive patients; (5) had severe heart disease, brain disease, lung disease, kidney disease, tumor disease, hemoglobin disease, or other systemic diseases; (6) withheld informed consent. [from the paper]

[from the registry]

Inclusion criteria

- (1) 18–65 years of age; (2) Diagnosed as mild to moderate COVID-19; (3) Be willing to sign informed consent; (4) The clinical assessment and condition of the subject does not influence the completion of the study.

Exclusion criteria :

- (1) Patients are diagnosed as a case of severe NCIP; (2) Patients are pregnant or breastfeeding women; (3) Patients have aspartate aminotransferase (AST) or alanine aminotransferase (ALT) > 5×UNL or creatinine clearance <50 ml / min; (4) Patients are allergic or intolerant to the proposed antiviral therapeutic drugs; (5) Patients are HIV-positive; (6) Patients with hemoglobin disease (7) Patients have severe heart disease, brain disease, lung disease, kidney disease, tumor or other severe systemic diseases; (8) Patients are not willing to provide signed informed consent.

[from the protocol]

Patients will be included from our study if they satisfy the following criteria: (1) 18 to 65 years of age; (2) diagnosed as mild to moderate COVID-19; (3) be willing to sign informed consent.

Patients who are diagnosed with severe COVID-19, or are pregnant or breastfeeding women, having aspartate aminotransferase or alanine aminotransferase >5 × upper normal limit or creatinine clearance <50 mL/min, are allergic or intolerant to the proposed antiviral therapeutic drugs, are human immunodeficiency virus-positive, having severe heart disease, brain disease, lung disease, kidney disease, neoplastic disease, hemolytic anemia, or other severe systemic diseases, or are not willing to provide signed informed consent, will be excluded.

4b Settings and locations where the data were collected

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Chongqing Public Health Medical Center.

Interventions

5 The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered

RBV was given by intravenous injection at a loading dose of 2g, followed by oral doses of 400–600 mg every 8 hours depending on patients' body weight, for 14 days. LPV/r was given

orally at a dose of 400 mg/100 mg per dose twice per day for 14 days. IFN- α was given by atomizing inhalation at a dose of 5 million U or 50 mg per dose twice a day for 14 days. Patients could additionally receive nasal cannula oxygen therapy and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) as demanded by their clinical conditions.

Outcomes

6a Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed

The primary outcome was the difference in the interval from baseline to SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acid negativity among the three antiviral treatment groups.

The secondary outcomes included the differences among the three groups in the rate of SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acid negativity at day 14, the mortality rate at day 28, the rate of patients re-classified as severe cases during the study period, the rate of adverse events during the study period, and the rate of therapeutic discontinuations due to adverse events during the study period.

SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acid negativity was defined as the presence of negative SARS-COV-2 results in at least two consecutive nasopharyngeal swabs by reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR), with an interval of at least 24 hours between the two time points of swab-taking. Of the two consecutive negative RT-PCR test results, the first negative result was used to calculate the interval between baseline and SARS-COV-2 nucleic acid negativity. [From the paper]

[From the registry] Outcome :

- *The time to 2019-nCoV RNA negativity in patients*
- *mortality on day 28*
- *The rate of negative 2019-nCoV RNA results at day 14*
- *the rate of aggravation*
- *the rate of adverse events*
- *The rate of discontinuations due to adverse events*

[From the protocol] *The study endpoints are: two consecutive negative 2019-nCoV RNA results after initiation of antiviral therapy at least 24 h apart; progression to severe COVID-19; completion of the entire therapeutic regimen and study patient visits; adjustment of medications due to poor prognosis or severe adverse events, or death.*

The primary outcome is the time to 2019-nCoV RNA negativity in patients. The secondary outcomes are: the rate of negative 2019-nCoV RNA results at day 14; the mortality rate for COVID-19 patients at day 28 after antiviral therapy; the rate of patients re-classified as severe

cases during the study period; the rate of adverse events during the study period, and the rate of therapeutic discontinuation due to adverse events during the study period.

6b Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons

None given.

Sample size

7a How sample size was determined

[From the paper] *We originally planned to recruit a total of 108 patients based on a power of 80%, and a level of confidence of 95%, while also considering a dropout rate of 10%, as described in our protocol.*

[From the protocol] *Our research is designed as an open-labeled, single-center, prospective, randomized and controlled clinical trial. We hope to enroll a sample size of 108 patients for this study, based on a power of 80%, and a level of confidence set at 95%, while also considering a dropout rate of 10%.*

7b When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines

None described.

Randomisation

Sequence generation

8a Method used to generate the random allocation sequence

None described.

8b Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)

All eligible patients were block randomized individually by means of random computer-generated lists, to one of three treatment groups: RBV+IFN- α , LPV/r+IFN- α , and RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α , with an allocation ratio of 1:1:1, and a block size of nine patients each.

Allocation concealment mechanism

9 Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until

interventions were assigned

None described.

Implementation

10 Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions

After COVID-19 patients were admitted, we approached those who might be eligible for our study and sought their consent for eligibility screening. After they provided their written informed consent, we assessed their eligibility for study inclusion, and only included those who met our inclusion criteria and who also did not meet the exclusion criteria of our study, in the study. Then, eligible patients were randomized to one of the three treatment groups at a ratio of 1:1:1 by means of the computer-generated random allocation schedule.

Blinding

11a If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how

Laboratory staff performing quantitative or qualitative testings were blinded to treatment allocation, whilst medical staff were not blinded.

11b If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions

Not described.

Statistical methods

12a Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes

[From the paper] *The Kaplan–Meier method was used to estimate median interval to SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acid negativity, and the p-value was calculated by log-rank testing. Hazard ratios with 95% confidence intervals were calculated by means of the Cox proportional-hazards model. Categorical variables were analyzed using the chi-squared (χ^2) test, or Fisher’s exact test. Data were analyzed using SPSS software Version 24 (IBM-SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.*

[From the protocol] *We will compare the study endpoints among the three arms using time-to-event methods with the Cox proportional-hazards model. The different categorical variables will be analyzed using the one-way analysis of variance. To describe the efficacy and safety of the three antiviral regimens, Kaplan-Meier estimates and a multivariate Cox proportional hazards model will be used to compare mortality of patients and adverse events*

among the three arms during the study period at day 28. A P-value of <0.05 will be deemed to confer statistical significance.

12b Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses
Not described.

Results

Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)

13a For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome

We therefore finally enrolled 101 participants in total. All of the 101 participants were enrolled between January 29, 2020 and February 25, 2020, and of these, 33 patients were randomly assigned to the RBV+IFN- α -treated group, 36 were assigned to the LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group, and 32 were assigned to the RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group. Of the 101 patients, five patients (5.0%) withdrew as a result of re-classification as severe COVID-19 cases, and 20 patients (19.8%) changed their treatment regimens subsequent to adverse events. Finally, 27 patients completed the regimen of RBV+IFN- α , 28 patients completed the regimen of LPV/r+IFN- α , and 21 patients completed the regimen of RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α , respectively. A flow diagram detailing the differences in numbers between the intention-to-treat population as compared with the per-protocol population is shown in Figure 1.

13b For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons

Figure 1. Flow-chart of the study

Recruitment

14a Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up

However, the effective and efficient control of the COVID-19 outbreak in Chongqing, due to well-planned and expeditiously executed public health measures in response to the outbreak, resulted in a relative scarcity of appropriate patients to recruit. We therefore finally enrolled 101 participants in total. All of the 101 participants were enrolled between January 29, 2020 and February 25, 2020.

14b Why the trial ended or was stopped

See 14a.

Baseline data

15 A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group

Yes.

Numbers analysed

16 For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups

We therefore finally enrolled 101 participants in total. All of the 101 participants were enrolled between January 29, 2020 and February 25, 2020, and of these, 33 patients were randomly assigned to the RBV+IFN- α -treated group, 36 were assigned to the LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group, and 32 were assigned to the RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group.

Outcomes and estimation

17a For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)

In the intention-to-treatment (ITT) population, the median intervals from baseline to SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acid negativity was 13 days, 12 days, and 15 days in the RBV+IFN- α -treated group, the LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group, and the RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group, respectively ($p=0.23$). Upon statistical analysis, no significant differences in median interval from baseline to SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acid negativity were found among these groups and between any two of the three groups. The hazard ratio of nucleic acid negativity in the group taking LPV/r+IFN- α was 1.50 (95% confidence interval [CI], 0.89, 2.52), and the hazard ratio of nucleic acid negativity in the group taking RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α was 1.39 (0.80, 2.41), compared with RBV+ IFN- α (Table 2 and Figure 2A).

In the ITT population, the SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acid negativity rates at day 14 in the RBV+IFN- α -treated group, the LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group and the RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group were 51.5% (17/33), 61.1% (22/36) and 46.9% (15/32) respectively, and 81.8% (27/33), 94.4% (34/36), 90.1% (29/32) respectively at day 28 (Figure 3A). However, the differences were statistically insignificant among the three groups, and between any two of the three groups.

We also assessed illness progression rates among the three groups by comparing different rates of patients re-classified as severe cases, and mortality rates during the study period. We found that one patient (3.0%) in the RBV+IFN- α -treated group, two patients (5.6%) in the LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group and two patients (6.3%) in the RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group had been re-classified as severe cases of COVID 19. However, no statistically significant difference in illness progression rates was observed among the three groups, and between any two of the three groups. Gratifyingly, there was no mortality in our cohort of 101 patients during the study period (Table 2).

17b For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended

Not reported.

Ancillary analyses

18 Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory

Harms

19 All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms⁴²)

A significantly higher rate of diarrhea and vomiting was observed in the RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α -treated group compared to the other two groups, in both the ITT This preprint research paper has not been peer reviewed. Electronic copy available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3576905> and PP populations. There were no significant differences in the rate of other adverse events among the three groups, including liver damage, electrolyte disorders, coagulation dysfunction, and cytopenias (Figures 4A and 4B). In addition, no patients appeared to develop any renal dysfunction in our study. We found that older patients had a higher rate of adverse events both in the ITT and PP populations, but this difference in rates of adverse events was not found to be statistically significant upon analysis (Figure 4C). Furthermore, we found that no statistically significant differences existed between adverse events in each gender in either the ITT population or the PP population (Figure 4D). No serious adverse events occurred during the course of the present study

Discussion

Limitations

20 Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses

There are a few limitations in our study. Firstly, the open-labeled design may have led to bias in the assessment of adverse events and clinical resolution. Nevertheless, centralization of randomization, and strict inclusion and exclusion criteria, are expected to have reduced this possibility. Secondly, this was a single-center trial with a limited number of participants in three arms, and thus, the results obtained at our center may not be representative of other hospitals

in China. Thirdly, we would have been able to better substantiate the effectiveness and safety of the different antiviral treatment regimens if control groups receiving placebo, or no intervention, had been incorporated into our study design.

Generalisability

21 Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings

Not discussed.

Interpretation

22 Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence

In conclusion, our results demonstrated that there was no statistically apparent difference among the three antiviral therapeutic regimens in terms of antiviral effectiveness in patients with mild to moderate COVID-19. This could imply that the antiviral effectiveness of LPV/r+IFN- α , RBV+IFN- α , and RBV+LPV/r+IFN- α for the management of COVID 19 is questionable. However, the very small possibility that these three regimens have similar to identical antiviral efficacy against SARS-CoV-2 cannot definitively excluded. Further, the combination of RBV and LPV/r is associated with a significant increase in gastrointestinal adverse events, suggesting that RBV and LPV/r should not be simultaneously administered to COVID-19 patients for the management of SARS-CoV-2 infection. We anticipate that these early findings may inform future effective management of COVID-19.

Other information

Registration

23 Registration number and name of trial registry

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Chongqing Public Health Medical Center (2020-002-01-KY), and was duly registered at the Chinese Clinical Trial Registry (ChiCTR2000029387).

<http://www.chictr.org.cn/showprojen.aspx?proj=48782>

Protocol

24 Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available

https://journals.lww.com/cmj/FullText/2020/05050/Comparative_effectiveness_and_safety_of_ribavirin.24.aspx

Funding

25 Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders

The funder of the study had no role in the study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, or writing of the report. The corresponding authors had full access to all the data in the study and had final responsibility for the decision to submit for publication.

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